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INNOVATIVE DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION BASED ON THE PRACTICAL EXAMPLE OF THE COMPANY "ZEDAZENI"

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyze the criteria for the effectiveness of digital marketing of the company "Zedazeni" on the modern stage in the conditions of Globalization and to search for ways of further development. The theoretical and methodological basis of the study is the relevant publications, as well as Internet Resources, which reflect the analysis and evaluation of the practical experience of the company "Zedazeni".

This article discusses the history, goal of "Zedazeni", as well as the export of products, the micro, macro environment of the company and the corresponding archetypes of products. A competitive analysis of Georgian beer market has been conducted. Innovative strategies of digital marketing have been identified. The positive aspects of digital marketing of "Zedazeni" on the modern stage have been identified. Also, as a conclusion, the criteria for its effectiveness have been formulated.

Keywords: *Digital, Marketing, Innovative, Strategy, Globalization, Company, "Zedazeni".*

When we hear the words "Georgian beer", we immediately think of the company "Zedazeni". The fact that "Zedazeni" is one of the most popular beers in Georgia is a fact. It is quite difficult to win the first place in Georgian beer market. Yes, "Zedazeni" managed to do this and in just 9 years occupied the largest segment of the market share in Georgian beer market.

JSC "Georgian Beer Company", created with national capital, began construction of the brewery "Zedazeni" in May 2011. The site for construction was chosen at the foot of Mount "Zedazeni", at the entrance to the village of Saguramo. The decisive role in choosing the site was played by the unique water that is found there. As the Management of "Georgian Beer Company" itself says, Mount "Zedazeni" creates a natural system that not only filters and dilutes water with the necessary minerals, but also charges it with amazing energy. So, the products that are made on this water are distinguished by their unique properties. Because water is a critical factor for this industry.

The construction and installation of state-of-the-art equipment were carried out by Czech, German, French, Austrian, Turkish, Polish, Slovenian and Ukrainian specialists, along with local Human Resources. All areas of the production cycle were equipped with equipment that is, in fact, the last word in the modern food industry.

At the beginning of 2012, the brewery was ready for trial brewing. On April 2 of the same year, the ceremonial opening of the "Zedazeni" brewery took place and the sale of its products throughout Georgia began. On April 25 of the same year, the first export shipment of "Zedazeni" products was also carried out. A new era of beer began on the Georgian market. It is worth noting that the "Zedazeni" factory was designed by the Czech company "ZVU POTEZ". 70 million euros were

invested in its construction, which is quite a large amount for Georgian capital. Currently, 700 people are employed in the production.

JSC "Georgian Beer Company" was founded with one goal: to become the leader of the Georgian beer and soft drinks market. As mentioned in the current article, within 7 months of the start of construction, an innovative type of beer factory was erected on an empty site and it became possible to start trial brewing of beer. The establishment of modern European standard production in such a short time was possible thanks to the experience and professionalism of the team. The company group has 20 years of successful experience in the Georgian beer and soft drinks market [1].

The brewery "Zedazeni" is equipped with the most modern European-made equipment. Among them, the bottling lines (glass bottles, PET bottles, cans, metal barrels) and the soft drinks workshop are manufactured by the German first-class manufacturer "KHS".

After a financial, legal and technical audit of the company's corporate governance system, the American premium brand "MILLER" was added to the "Zedazeni" beer portfolio. This business transaction once again confirms that the "Zedazeni" enterprise fully meets all the world standards and requirements necessary for the production of high-quality, premium brands.

"MILLER" produced in our country is sold in Georgia, Azerbaijan, Armenia and the Middle East.

"MILLER" is a light, American, premium-class beer. Its special taste is created not only by the recipe, but also by the unique brewing technology – four-fold filtration.

"Everything is best, made with the best ingredients" - to make the motto a reality, all MILLER production companies use specialized malt and hops,

which are specially processed to give the beer a less bitter taste.

“Georgian Beer Company” is distinguished by its innovation in the beer market. The Management turned the difficulties caused by the pandemic into an opportunity and used this time to make the Georgian beer market even more interesting. After almost 3 years of negotiations, additional investments, experimental brewing, enterprise audits and the introduction of Western standards in Management, today the company proudly announces that the “Zedazeni” Brewery is a partner of the world giant of the beer industry – “Molson Coors” and, as mentioned in the current article, is a licensee of “MILLER” in our region and other countries of the Middle East [2].

Since the establishment of the Georgian Beer Company, TBC Bank has been its partner. Within the framework of this cooperation, TBC has provided financing of up to 270 million GEL to Zedazeni.

The Georgian Competition and Consumer Protection Agency has identified a concentration in the beer and non-alcoholic beverage market, which was subject to mandatory prior notification. According to the agency, the issue concerns the acquisition of a 100% stake in Zedazeni 2012 LLC by JSC Georgian Beer Company in 2023. As stated in the relevant order, by the decision of the agency, JSC Georgian Beer Company was fined GEL 40,000 for failure to notify the concentration. Moreover, the agency approved the concentration, as it considers the transaction to be fully compatible with the competitive environment.

"According to the materials received and processed by the Agency, it was determined that in 2023, 215 companies operated in the non-alcoholic beverages market, the market volume was 464,757,669 liters, and the market concentration HHI index was 2,590. As for the beer market, in the same year, 75 companies operated in the market, the market volume was 90,532,597 liters, and the market concentration HHI index was 1,888.

According to the Agency's assessment, the non-alcoholic beverages market is highly concentrated, however, the concentration index slightly exceeds the maximum index of a moderately concentrated market (2,250). The beer market is moderately concentrated, and the distribution services market is low-concentrated. Taking this into account, the Agency decided, The implemented concentration does not have a significant impact on the relevant market and is compatible with the competitive environment [3].

“According to the news covered in the media from the beer industry, JSC “Georgian Beer Company” is leading”. It is noteworthy that according to the media statistics of the beer market of “IPM Market Intelligence Caucasus”, 52% of the media activities of Georgian beer industry fall on “Georgian Beer Company”, its share of media activity was 33% in 2019. However, the most interesting thing that was published in this article is the market share of beer companies in the beer market.

The fact is stubborn: “Zedazeni” is undoubtedly the first in the Georgian beer market in terms of the number of consumers, which means that its market share is also large.

84% of the surveyed consumers have a positive attitude towards the “Zedazeni” company. This cannot be said about one of its competitors - “Natakhtari”, towards which only 38% have a positive attitude. A positive consumer directly indicates the size of the market growth coefficient. The company also has a high market growth coefficient, because quite a lot of people have a positive attitude towards it, and a satisfied consumer is a direct sign of the company's development in the market. “Georgian Beer Company” really tried to diversify, which is why they have a wide variety of products today, they have: beers, iced tea, natural juices, a large selection of lemonades, cola and even energy drinks. But when they did this, they did not pursue permanent diversification, they began to work on export-oriented work with those already diversified existing products, which means that they started market development in order to be able to export more products, and exporting a large number of products in itself once again speaks of the success of the company.

The value proposition is very important for a company, because it is thanks to it that it is able to create targeted prices. The value chain is the sum of direct and auxiliary activities that create added value and through which the organization produces, distributes and sells its products.

Since Heineken, Efes or Estrella beers offer a value proposition that is more or less the same, based on logic, we can conclude that “Zedazeni”'s value proposition is more or less the same, as the company offers quality at a lower price. It is worth noting that “Zedazeni” does not have the 157-year experience and international reputation of Heineken (which is one of the determinants of price), however, its products are truly high-quality and meet European standards.

It is probably impossible to talk about a digital marketing strategy without positioning the company's products. In order to determine the positioning of the product, it is necessary to touch on the consumer segment. It is worth noting that consumers buy “Zedazeni”'s products with utilitarian behavior. According to Engel's law, a person's spending on a product increases with the increase in his income. We compared the price of one of the premium beers, “Heineken”, with the price of “Zedazeni”. It goes without saying that the price of “Heineken” is significantly higher (which is logical), and then we thought about what the capital of the “Zedazeni” buyer is, what level their material life has reached, and so on. The situation in Georgia is catastrophic in this regard. The devaluation of the Lari is accompanied by inflation, which to some extent requires innovative companies to reduce costs, and, of course, the Human Resources employed in reducing these costs are being used up involuntarily.

Given the relevance of this article, we will discuss the advantages of digital marketing of the company “Zedazeni”: The first thing we noticed upon entering the site is that the website has an adaptive design, that is, this is one of the approaches to website design that allows the so-called. Design and code to match the screen size of different devices. Thanks to the adaptive design, the “Zedazeni” site has optimal visibility on any device, which eliminates site malfunctions as much as possible. The second thing we discovered about this

site was that it fully meets the design concept (its design is creative). The technical side of web design is also performed at a very high level, that is, the graphic templates of the internal pages of the site are in harmony with each other. Since today we cannot meet a site that does not have Integration with the Management system, we did not consider this an advantage, although it is worth noting that it also has it. Integration with the system is the unity of a multifaceted structure, a large amount of information, sophisticated design and easy multi-functional management in the site (a modern website must have all of the above to be considered a complete site). We really liked the so-called site promotion, because as soon as we started searching for it in the Google search engine, our device immediately found it very easily. A special advantage that the "Zedazeni" website has is that the design is directly related to its content, that is, drinks. So, as a citizen of Georgia and a beer consumer, we give the "Zedazeni" website a 10/10 rating.

In this section, we will look at the export of "Zedazeni" products. The company has always expanded its market and exported its products. The addition of new markets increased exports by 50%-60%. "Zedazeni" exports increased because the market itself expanded, as they began to develop new markets at the end of 2019. Exports would have increased by 2 times if not for the global pandemic. As noted in the current article, "Zedazeni" also ships beer to European countries, as well as Central Asia and Russia.

It is logical that if a company is not influential, purposeful, has large capital and does not have a quality product, it will not be able to export its products. However, since the "Georgian Beer Company" managed to do this, we cannot physically call it a weak or marketing-failed firm; on the contrary, it deserves great praise, because the company, in which, as stated in the current article, 70 million euros have been invested, plays a fairly large role in the country's trade balance (despite the fact that the balance is still negative, imports sharply exceed exports).

This time we will consider the company's Macro Environment. Like the assessment of the Micro Environment, it is quite difficult to assess the macro environment. We need to take into account a lot of factors and, at the same time, it is necessary not to confuse them, because we may encounter certain problems in our assessment of the macro environment, so we made a fundamental decision to analyze the macro environment with the so-called PESTEL analysis. PESTEL analysis is one of the most optimal analyses for studying the macro environment, which includes Social, Technological, Legal, etc. Consideration of the macro environment from a social, technological, legal, etc. perspective. Let's analyze them one by one:

Social factors - it is logical that it implies the segmentation of the company's customers. With Geographical segmentation, the company's main marketing target is Georgians, as evidenced by its name - "Zedazeni", which immediately brings to mind the "Zedazeni" temple. But since "Zedazeni" has also exported its product, we can safely say that its indirect targets are also foreigners. Demographically, again,

based on the name, the product is aimed at Orthodox Christians. As for segmentation by income, given that beer is sold in cheap alcoholic beverages, and "Zedazeni" is cheaper than premium beers, we can fundamentally conclude that their product is aimed at people with average incomes, since premium beers are also imported to Georgia, which are presumably intended for consumers with higher incomes or for fans of specific companies.

Now let's move on to psychographic segmentation. Of course, since there is a direct proportional relationship between income segmentation and psychographic segmentation, it is easy to say that "Zedazeni" beer is largely intended for the middle social class.

Technological factors – so far "Zedazeni" strictly follows innovations and beer is bottled using modern European equipment. Accordingly, the Georgian beer company does not have a problem in this regard.

Legal factors – this mainly refers to discriminatory laws, or laws on "protection of consumer rights". Yes, Georgia does have a law on "protection of consumer rights", this law was adopted by the Parliament of Georgia on March 20, 1996. It does not belong to organic laws, it is an ordinary law and includes relevant articles and clauses.

Environmental factors – The last negative environmental factor can be considered the Coronavirus, which has caused severe damage not only to "Zedazeni", but also to top-level International Brands.

To be fair, it is worth noting that "Zedazeni" has the right marketing vision and strategy. In order for the company not only to succeed in the market, but also to gain recognition and fame, it needs to pay close attention to branding, which is what makes an ordinary product a brand. In this part of the article, we will analyze the corresponding archetypes of the products of the company "Zedazeni":

THE HERO

The hero archetype fits very well with the beer "Ragnar", because its advertising calls on potential consumers to be brave, to dare and try this beer, after which they will be brave in life. "Ragnar" belongs to the group of products that protect their dignity.

THE INNOCENT

Since "Innocent" is an optimistic and positive brand, the main feature of which is a feeling of happiness, here we remembered the juice "Chero" from the products of "Zedazeni". Chero's slogan has always been: "Don't Stop Happiness!" Therefore, it is not surprising that it belongs to the innocent among archetypes.

THE EXPLORER

We had to think about this archetype, because the explorer wants new adventures. However, we soon came to "Zedazeni", which product belonged to the above-mentioned archetype. We remembered the description of the iced tea – "Gurieli", which we encounter on the main website of "Zedazeni": "If you are curious, thirsty for new discoveries and knowledge of the diversity of the world, you have creative impulses or you are just very hot, drink iced tea!" It is easy to guess that this product is an explorer with archetypal branding.

THE REGULAR

Beer and lemonade “Zedazeni” belong to this archetype. They are nothing special, delicious drinks that have managed to thrive in the competitive Georgian beer and lemonade market.

We looked at the company “Zedazeni” with a systematic approach and in this case, we matched the brand itself to some archetype. Of course, “Zedazeni” can be attributed to the usual ones, because reliability and practicality are always in the first place for this brand.

Conclusion: In the end, we can conclude that “Zedazeni” is one of the most successful companies in the Georgian beer market and, as the analysis showed, the best. It has gained trust among consumers, which opens up even greater potential. The strength of the company is also emphasized by the fact that it exports a fairly large volume of products. The success of “Zedazeni” was primarily determined by large financing, as a source of attracting financial resources, and we cannot leave without assessing the diligent work of the value chain of this company, that is, various departments, in such value-creating activities as: product design, production, marketing, delivery and product support. Considering that the success of the company depends on how well each department manages to add these values to the buyer and how well

the activities of different departments are coordinated, the company has a truly strong and coordinated value chain, because they perfectly manage its marketing complex. However, Georgia is not yet among the TOP beer producing countries. The first reason for this is that “Zedazeni” is still developing and has not reached the appropriate level for itself, as well as other Georgian brands. We believe that they will definitely develop, but for this we need to support them.

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